

HF-free microwave assisted dissolution of soil samples for quantitative assessment of potassium[†]

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Abstract : HF-free microwave assisted soil dissolution method has been developed for potassium analysis using HNO₃ and HClO₄. The developed method will be helpful for K analysis by AAS, ICP-OES or ICP-MS. Twelve soil samples were subjected to digestion in microwave digester for extracting out potassium. Even after vigorous digestion, about 20% residue was observed. It has been confirmed by γ -spectrometry with the help of highly shielded high-purity Germanium (HPGe) detector that the residue does not contain any ⁴⁰K, which in turn suggests that the total K has been transferred to the solution.

Keywords : Microwave digestion, soil, potassium analysis, gamma spectrometry, ⁴⁰K.

Introduction

Today's Analytical Chemistry for quantitative determination of various elements present in the matrix is equipped with state-of-art instruments like AAS, XRF, ICP class of instruments (ICPOES and ICPMS) and many others. Highly sensitive analytical methods are available where chemical pre-treatments are not required at all. Instrumental Neutron Activation Analysis (INAA), Energy Dispersive (ED)- or Wavelength Dispersive (WD)-X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF), Particle Induced X-Ray Emission (PIXE), Heavy Ion induced X-Ray Emission (HIXE), Particle Induced Gamma Ray Emission (PIGE), etc. are examples of such non-destructive methods. Recently we have developed a non-destructive method for K-analysis, which relies on the linear relationship between K-40 and total K¹. In this method huge background of naturally occurring K-40 was suppressed by using a heavy lead shield along with different graded shielding. Later this method was successfully applied to determine K in ancient glass beads².

On the other hand, sometimes chemical pre-treatments are referred to as superior and more authentic for quanti-

tative analysis of an element. Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), Radiochemical Neutron Activation Analysis (RNAA), and the ultra sensitive ICP instruments belong to this class. The chemical pre-treatment includes removal of extraneous materials, washing, pulverization, heating till constant weight, digestion, dissolution of the sample, etc. Sample dissolution is an important analytical step for complex geological samples like rock, soil, sediment, which are composed of dissimilar organic and inorganic components³. The classical acid digestion of soil or rock samples is time consuming and requires huge amount of acids, which is unwanted from the viewpoint of green chemistry as well as personnel safety. Microwave assisted acid decomposition and analytical techniques are rescue to this problem and have been proved environment friendly and beneficial in obtaining data precision and extraction accuracy⁴.

There is no universal protocol for sample dissolution either by classical or by microwave assisted technique. The dissolution technique is dependent on type of sample, its physical form, or on the analyte of interest. Till date microwave heating under specified temperature, pressure

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

and time have been performed for a wide range of samples including soil⁴, sediment⁵, rock⁶, etc.

For digestion of geological samples, either single acid (HCl, HNO₃, HF, HClO₄, H₂SO₄) or mixture of acids (HCl + HNO₃, HF + HNO₃, HF + HClO₄, HCl + HNO₃ + H₂SO₄, etc.) have been used depending upon sample size and other conditions⁷⁻⁹. For most cases, HF, in combination with other acids, is used to break the strong Si-O bonding of silicate minerals present in various environmental matrices⁷. Bettinelli *et al.*⁴ had used mixture of HF-HCl-HNO₃ (1 : 3 : 1) as a complete digestion method for soil and sediment prior to ICP-OES measurement of heavy metals. Chen and Ma¹⁰, who compared three commonly used aqua-regia digestion methods concluded HF-HCl-HNO₃ combination has slightly better decomposition ability. Similar acid combination was reported by Sandroni and Smith¹¹ for metal analysis of sludge, soil and sediment samples, by Perez-Santana *et al.*¹² for determination of trace elements in sediment samples and by Kadi¹³ for studying the chemical composition of roadside soil samples.

However, HF aided dissolution processes apprehensive to pneumatic nebulization in atomic spectrometry, AAS, ICP-OES or ICP-MS (unless special arrangement is made) and may pose threat to various high-tech parts of the instrument. HF concentration is reduced by addition of boric acid, which in turn participates in clogging of the nebulizer with significantly enhancing total dissolved solid content in sample solution. This results in poor data quality having low accuracy and precision. To avoid HF, Hassan *et al.*¹⁴ successfully modified the microwave heating parameters by maximizing ramp temperature, digestion time, minimizing sample-to-acid ratio and used HNO₃ alone or HNO₃-HCl mixture. Similarly Chand and Prasad⁵ investigated heavy metal in marine sediments, Islam *et al.*¹⁵ assessed trace metals in differ-

ent soil samples, Sastre *et al.*¹⁶ determined metals in environmental samples without use of hydrofluoric acid at the time of digestion.

The present study is aimed to develop a reliable HF-free microwave assisted digestion method for leaching out total potassium content from soil or sediment samples without HF treatment, which may be used afterwards for AAS or ICP-OES analysis of K.

Experimental

Materials :

The chemical reagents 65% HNO₃ suprapur was procured from Merck, Germany and 70% HClO₄ GR was procured from Merck, India.

Instrumentation :

Acid digestion was done using CEM MARS Xpress microwave digester consisting of cylindrical Teflon tubes to hold samples for digestion. De-ionized water for the experiment was obtained from Thermoscientific Barnstead Nanopure water purification system. Gamma spectrometric studies were done using reverse electrode coaxial high purity Ge (HPGe) detector (CANBERRA) with 50% relative efficiency and 2.1 keV resolution at 1.33 MeV. The setup was shielded inside CANBERRA model 747 lead shielding of 9.5 mm thick low carbon outer jacket, 10 cm thick bulk lead with graded shielding of 1 mm tin and 1.6 mm copper, thereby cutting the background interference in obtaining very low ⁴⁰K activity in soil matrix. All the associated electronics were procured from Canberra.

Methods :

Total twelve soil samples were air-dried and pulverized followed by heating under infrared (IR) lamp until constant weight. Afterwards, 250 mg of soil sample was put into clean Teflon vessels of CEM MARS Xpress microwave digester. Each sample was digested with addi-

Table 1. Instrumental operating parameters for microwave digestion using CEM MARS Xpress

Amount of sample	Acid mixture	Volume used	Power	Temperature	Rising time	Holding time
250 mg	HNO ₃ + HClO ₄	4 mL + 4 mL	800 W	120 °C	10 min	60 + 60 min

tion of 2 mL suprapur HNO₃ + 2 mL HClO₄ for 60 min at 120 °C. Same step was repeated again for another 60 min, followed by addition of 12 mL de-ionized water. Table 1 shows the operating conditions for microwave digestion. Even after the vigorous digestion some residue was observed (~20% by of initial amount) in each of the soil samples. After centrifugation at 5000 rpm for 10 min the supernatant was segregated from the undigested residue by filtration with Whatman 42 filter papers. To know whether the undigested residue contain potassium or not, the residual solid precipitates along with the filter papers were preserved in plastic petri-plates for gamma spectrometric analysis.

Background spectrum for 150000 s was taken using dummy petri-plate containing unused filter paper. Similarly, gamma spectra for original soil samples and the solid undigested residues were taken for 150000 s. Also all the residual samples were mixed together and again gamma spectrometric analysis was done.

Results and discussion

Potassium has three naturally occurring isotope, ³⁹K

(93.2581%), ⁴⁰K (0.0117%) and ⁴¹K (6.7302%). Out of these three isotopes, ⁴⁰K is a primordial, naturally occurring long-lived ($T_{1/2} = 1.248 \times 10^9$ a) radionuclide¹⁷. The amount of ⁴⁰K, in principle, has linear relationship with total K because of its universally fixed abundance. Therefore, assessment of ⁴⁰K would tell us the amount of total K in natural samples. Fig. 1(A) shows the gamma spectrum of one soil sample in the 1400–1500 keV energy region, showing the photo-peak of ⁴⁰K at 1460.83 keV. We have compared the area under the photopeaks of 1460.83 keV in the soil sample with a 50 Bq ⁴⁰K sample and found the activity of ⁴⁰K in the soil sample 1 is 884.6 Bq/kg, which corresponds to 28.5 g natural K/kg or 2.85% K in the soil sample. Fig. 1(B) is the background-subtracted spectrum of all the undigested residual samples collected together. It clearly shows that the activity of ⁴⁰K (Bq) in all the left-over residue is below the gamma spectrometric limit of detection. Therefore, it can be confidently concluded that the undigested residue after microwave digestion of the soil sample by HNO₃ + HClO₄ acid mixture does not contain any potassium. The flow chart of the developed method is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Background subtracted gamma spectrum of a soil sample taken over 150000 s showing ⁴⁰K photopeak at 1460.83 keV (A); background subtracted gamma spectrum of residue of all the samples after microwave digestion and filtration of the supernatant, showing no ⁴⁰K in the residue.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the developed digestion method.

Conclusion

Microwave digestion system is greener dissolution technique, as it requires much less amount of acid in dissolution of soil, rock and sediment and also less time consuming. The present study shows that HF-free acid combination $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{HClO}_4$ can be used for microwave-assisted digestion for analyte specific (potassium) dissolution of soil samples. The validation of the technique has been done by gamma spectrometric study. The developed method quantitatively transfers all the K into the solution without using HF acid.

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